

Report on the application of the tool for assets evaluation in the Museo Valle di Blenio and prioritization of interventions

Museo Valle di Blenio, Via al Museo di Blenio 9, Lottigna, Acquarossa, Ticino, Switzerland
July 2020

SUPSI University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland, Department for Environment Constructions and Design, Laboratory of visual culture / Institute of Earth Sciences

Iolanda Pensa, Cristian Scapozza, Marta Pucciarelli
Deliverable D.T1.2.2

Activity A.T1.2 Set up of methodology for the evaluation of cultural assets and prioritization of securing & salvaging interventions

Pilot area

The application of the tool for assets evaluation focused on the Museo Valle di Blenio, an historical and ethnographic museum located in the ancient palace called *Palazzo dei Landfogti* (House of Landfogti, also called *Palazzo del Pretorio*; Pretorio's Palace) in Lottigna, Municipality of Acquarossa, Canton of Ticino, Switzerland (Fig. 1).

The *Palazzo dei Landfogti* in Lottigna is the main seat of the Museo Valle di Blenio, who manage also the seat of *Cà da Rivöi* in Olivone. This palace of administrative origins, situated in the middle Blenio Valley, was built at the beginning of the 16th century, on older walls, by Gian Domenico Cima from Aquila and was used, between 1550 and 1798, as the seat of the bailiffs of the Cantons of Uri, Schwyz and Nidwalden managing the Blenio Valley during the *Ancien Régime*. It became *Palazzo del Pretorio* with the independence of the Canton Ticino in 1803 and it housed the District Court until 1891 and is the seat of the Museo Valle di Blenio since 1979. The Museo Valle di Blenio is member of the Swiss Museum Association (VMS/AMS), of the Associazione dei musei etnografici ticinesi (AMET) and is recognised as a regional museum by the Cantonal administration of Canton Ticino (Centro di dialettologia e di etnografia CDE).

The Blenio Valley's geographical locations has the undoubted advantages of been easily accessible both from the north of the Alps and from the rest of the Canton Ticino and neighbouring Lombardy region, thanks to its proximity to the AlpTransit railway line (in yellow in Fig. 2) and the Gotthard highway axis (Fig. 2). The Museo Valle di Blenio is located along the historic route that leads to the Lukmanier and Greina Passes, which have been frequented since prehistoric times. The Lukmanier Pass in particular was already widely exploited in Roman times and, due to its particularity of being the only pass in the Pennine, Lepontine and Rhaetian Alps situated at an altitude of less than 2000 m above sea level, it constituted from the VII-VIII to the XII century a transit route used very intensively as the most direct transit route between Milan and Constance/Basel, known as the *Via Francisca del Lucomagno* (in green in Fig. 2).

Fig. 1: Location of the Museo Valle di Blenio in the Southern Swiss Alps (red label). Basemap from <https://map.geo.admin.ch>

Fig 2: Location of the Museo Valle di Blenio (which manage since 2020 also the seat of Cà da Rivöi in Olivone) and the eleven other organizations of the cultural-scientific framework of the Blenio valley (see Tab. 1). Cartography: Cristian Scapozza. Base maps: DEM25, ©swisstopo.

Fig 3: Location of the Museo Valle di Blenio (red label) in the hamlet of Lottigna, Municipality of Acquarossa. Basemap from <https://map.geo.admin.ch>

Tab. 1: List of the eleven cultural and scientific institutions active in the Blenio Valley shown in Fig. 2.

N.	Locality	Organisation
1	Campo Blenio	Piccolo museo della radio e della fotografia
2	Acquacalda	Centro Pro Natura Lucomagno
3	Olivone	Fondazione Alpina per le Scienze della Vita (FASV)
4	Aquila	Piccolo museo delle scatole di latta
5	Dangio-Torre	Fondazione La Fabbrica del Cioccolato
6	Castro	Fondazione Atelier Genucchi
7	Acquarossa	Cinema Teatro Blenio
8	Casserio	Fondazione Archivio Fotografico Roberto Donetta
9	Dongio	Fondazione Voce di Blenio
10	Semione	Associazione amici del Castello di Serravalle
11	Malvaglia	Atelier Titta Ratti

Relevance of the Museo Valle di Blenio

Cristian Scapozza is a member of SUPSI research team for the project CHEERS and he is the curator of the Museo Valle di Blenio. This double role allowed us to test the tool, to fully involve the relevant stakeholders on a specific case study, to support the improvement of the emergency procedures in a museum in Ticino and to develop a scalable process. The methodology applied to this specific historical and ethnographic museum is shared with other ethnographic museums in Ticino through their association (AMET Associazione Musei Etnografici Ticinesi).

Cultural Heritage

The House of Landfogti or Pretorio's Palace is a Swiss cultural property of national significance (class A) included in the [Swiss Inventory of Cultural Property of National and Regional Significance](#) (Fig. 4) with the identification number 5527. In the Inventario dei beni culturali of the Canton Ticino, the Museo Valle di Blenio is identified as object A1777.

Fig. 4: [Map of the Swiss Inventory of Cultural Property of National and Regional Significance](#). The red label indicated the Museo Valle di Blenio. Basemap from <https://map.geo.admin.ch>

Managing stakeholders

The assessment involved the team of the museum (the current curator and protagonists of the museum history, such as the former president of the museum, the former curator and one of the guardians), representatives of the Ticino Canton, the Civil Protection, the Centre for dialectology and ethnography (responsible for the coordination of the regional ethnographic museums), the Association of Ethnographic Museum of Ticino. The former curator of the museums is an art historian specialised in the collection and in the cultural heritage of the area, the honorary president of the museum is an expert of the history of the institution and of the territory and the curator Cristian Scapozza is a physical geographer also researcher at SUPSI and directly engaged in the CHEERS project.

Tab. 2: List of stakeholders involved in the assessment of the Museo Valle di Blenio.

Name	Affiliation	Role
Cristian Scapozza (CS)	Museo Valle di Blenio / SUPSI - DACD - IST	Curator / senior researcher
Iolanda Pensa (IP)	SUPSI - DACD - LCV	Principal investigator project CHEERS
Patrizia Pusterla Cambin (PPC)	Museo Valle di Blenio	Former curator
Fortunato Pezzatti (FP)	Museo Valle di Blenio	Honorary president
Letizia Genucchi Strazzini (LGS)	Museo Valle di Blenio	Guardian
Roland Hochstrasser (RH)	Ticino Canton - Culture and university studies / Divisione della Cultura e degli studi universitari	Collaborator (president of AMET - the association of ethnographic museums of Ticino)
Andrea A Marca (AAM)	Centre for dialectology and ethnography / Centro di dialettologia e di etnografia (CDE)	Representative of ethnographic museums
Filippo Jauch (FJ)	Civil protection - Protezione civile 3 valli (PCi 3Valli)	Responsible for the protection of cultural heritage in case of emergency

Stakeholders - Ethnographic Museums in Ticino, Switzerland

Stakeholders involved in the assessment, Blenio Museum, 12 February 2020

Designing hazard scenarios

Natural Hazards

Considering the natural hazard degree mapping and the indicative hazard phenomena mapping, the hamlet of Lottigna is comprised between two avalanche channels (in light red in Fig. 5) and is comprised in the area of a deep-seated gravitational slope deformation (DSGSD) (in ochre in Fig. 5). As this DSGSD is currently quiescent, there is no direct hazard coming from this mass movement in the entire area of the Lottigna hamlet. A small rockfall zone is mapped just north of the church (brown) and a deep rockslide area is present south of the hamlet (area with inclined bars). However, both phenomena do not have an effect on the Museo Valle di Blenio and, as a consequence, the museum is not directly subject to natural hazards.

Fig. 5: Indicative hazard phenomena map for the Lottigna hamlet. To note the two avalanche channels north and south of the hamlet (light red) and the presence of a DSGSD area covering the entire territory of Lottigna (ochre). Basemap: Piano Zone di Pericolo (Hazard Zone Plan or PZP) of the Canton Ticino, <https://www.sitmap.ti.ch/index.php?ct=pericolie>

Past natural events

During the 2005–2010 winters, problems related to the snow fall from the electric cables caused electricity supply interruption. This aspect, however, did not affect directly the building or the museum's collection. Some cases of water infiltration from the floor at the ground floor, where the water had reached a few centimetres thick, were documented in the past. At the second floor, there were slight water infiltrations due to the displacement of the stone roofing, the integrity of which is monitored annually. The last case was documented in spring 2020. There have never been any water contributions due to a broken boiler or pipework. There are no cases of frost in the pipes, as during the winter the main water pipe is interrupted and antifreeze is added to the sink and toilet. The construction of an external drainage as a solution to reduce the supply of moisture and water infiltration at the ground floor is under discussion.

Potential future hazards

Although the area is potentially subject to natural hazards, the Museo Valle di Blenio is not subject to landslide or avalanche risk. The problems related to the electricity supply will only improve in the near future as the burial of power lines is expected. An assessment of the potential trees falls due to the wind, that could impact the walls of the museum, was performed after the suggestion from the civil protection in February 2020 and two trees were cut at the end of June 2020. In next future, an evaluation of the possible instability of terracing walls located upstream of the main building, which could become unstable in case of heavy rain, is also planned.

The possibility of a fire happening in the area is much higher than the risk of other natural events. Therefore, it was suggested by the museum curator and SUPSI researcher on the project CHEERS to focus on the risk of fire as a realistic scenario.

Past experiences of fires of cultural heritage in Ticino have caused enormous damage to buildings, which necessitated a decade-long reconstruction and restoration process. The case of the fire of the Church of Santa Maria delle Grazie in Bellinzona in 1996, deeply affected the citizenship, but it also allowed to put into practice for the first time the new national and cantonal government policies, approved immediately after the outbreak of the fire (for a detailed description on the event see Deliverable: D.T1.1.1, Section “Fires”, Paragraph “Case study: Catastrophic fire of the Church of Santa Maria delle Grazie, Bellinzona, Switzerland”, pp. 89-91).

One year after the catastrophic fire of the Church of Santa Maria delle Grazie indeed, even not directly correlated to it, the Law for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of the 13th May 1997 was issued, specifying responsibilities, instruments and measures of protection in case of natural disaster. That law allowed to start on 2002 the census of all the cultural goods set in the Canton of Ticino area (more than 120,000), to index them in the SIBC-Information System of Cultural Goods and to prepare a registry of the goods of local or cantonal interest to be protected in case of natural disaster (almost 5,000) according to the federal regulations. Canton of Ticino's cultural goods registry only includes the goods of cantonal or local interest whose protection has already been ascribed with in a Cantonal Use Planning (IT: Piano direttore cantonale) or in a Municipal Development Plans (IT: Piano regolatore comunale), that collects administrative, estate, descriptive, typological, scientific and geo-referenced information. Recently fire-fighting simulations have been carried out by the civil protection in collaboration with the fire department for the protection of cultural heritage of the Blenio Valley. In particular the CHEERS' team has assisted to the fire-fighting simulation of intervention carried out on the San Martino Church in the Municipality of Olivone the 26th September 2019.

However, not all the cultural heritage institutions still have an emergency plan for their building in case of disaster.

Cultural heritage being evaluated

The ethnographic collection of the Museo Val di Blenio counts approximately 1500 objects. Part of them (743 objects) are archived online on the Centro di dialettologia e di etnografia (CDE) website: http://www.e-cde.ti.ch/bellinzona/eMuseumPlus?service=direct/1/ResultLightboxView/moduleBottomContextFunctionBar.bottomNavigator.next&sp=10&sp=Scollection&sp=SfieldValue&sp=0&sp=0&sp=3&sp=Slightbox_3x4&sp=12&sp=Sdetail&sp=0&sp=F&sp=24

The size of the museum collection, together with the diversity of the type of objects, made it impossible to apply the evaluation procedure in a systematic way to all museums' objects. Therefore, a selection of cultural objects of the collection to be evaluated was performed. The goals of the selection of the objects to safeguard in case of emergency are:

1. to test the CHEERS evaluation methodology;
2. to draft a museum protection plan

The selection of the objects involved the team of the Museo Valle di Blenio with different expertise in the field of cultural heritage and natural hazards: an art historian, an expert of the history of the institution and of the territory, the guardian of the museum, an ethnographer, a physical geographer (actual curator of the museum), and a representative of the civil protection. The current and previous curator projected on the meeting room the photographs of objects of the collection by presenting them in relation to the floor, the room and section of the museums where they are exhibited. A freewheeling discussion followed with all the participants who defined a list of objects by mutual agreement.

The criteria used in the selection process includes:

- the diversity of the typology of the object
- the representativeness of the object with the museum collection.

The results of the selection include a palette of 10 movable assets representing the museum' collection, classified as ethnographic objects, objects related to sacred art, and contemporary art objects.

Tab. 3 presents the 10 selected objects, which are identified by the code of the museum's catalogue of objects, image, description, dimension, material, classification of the object in the collection (ethnographic object, sacred art object, contemporary art object) and vulnerability. The vulnerability of the objects has been defined on a scale between a range from 1 (none) to 5 (very high).

Tab. 3: List of cultural heritage objects to be evaluated.

Code	Picture	Description	Dimension	Material	Typology	Vulnerability
LOT-1992.0061		Mobile step for <i>rascane</i> (i.e. outdoor dryer for rye)	81 x 20 x 9 cm	chestnut wood	Ethnographic object	2
LOT-1992.0122		"Prea" tool (literally "stone" in dialect) made of Baveno granite used to smash cocoa seeds with a rolling pin	60 x 40 x 45 cm (2 people needed)	Natural stone (Baveno granite)	Ethnographic object	1

LOT-1992.0316-0321		Series of soapstone pans produced before 1868 by the <i>U/turnill</i> atelier in Val di Carassino	maximum diameter: 16.5 cm	Natural stone (soapstone or steatite)	6 ethnographic objects	2
LOT-1992.0431		White brocade tunic with embroidery of the seventeenth century, representing Noah's Ark.	96 x 124 cm	Textile	Sacred art	4
LOT-1992.0444		Sculpture of the group of apostles, first half of the 16 th century.	17 x 102 x 78 cm Movable object (2 people needed)	Basswood	Sacred art	5
LOT-1998.0014		Fresco of the Nativity in the <i>Hortus conclusus</i> with S. Caterina (?) and S. Rocco	4 x 66 x 142 cm Movable object (2 people)	Fragments of fresco	Sacred art	4
LOT-2005.0008		19 th century copper and wood chocolate maker	21 x 9 x 18 cm	Copper and wood	Ethnographic object	3
LOT-2011.0018		Ambrosian ostensory, or ostensory reliquary, first half of the 16 th century	12 x 12 x 26 cm	Golden wood	Sacred art	5

nn		"Aurora", plaster sculpture by Giovanni Genucchi, 70s	42 x 15 x 18 cm	Plaster	Contemporary art object	3
nn		Brown peasant costume with handkerchief	60 x 120 cm	Textile	Ethnographic object	4

The evaluation

The evaluation process was conducted on Wednesday 12 February 2020 at the Museo Valle di Blenio during a meeting with representative stakeholders (See Tab. 4). The meeting involved six participants and the methodology for evaluating the values of the museum's collection were translated into Italian and explained orally by Cristian Scapozza, SUPSI researcher of the project CHEERS and curator of the Museo Valle di Blenio.

Tab 4: List of stakeholders who have participated to the meeting the 12 February 2020 at the Museo Valle di Blenio.

Name	Affiliation	Role
Cristian Scapozza (CS)	Museo Valle di Blenio SUPSI - DACD - IST	Curator, physical geographer and SUPSI researcher for project CHEERS
Patrizia Pusterla Cambin (PPC)	Museo Valle di Blenio	Former curator
Fortunato Pezzatti (FP)	Museo Valle di Blenio	Honorary president
Letizia Genucchi Strazzini (LGS)	Museo Valle di Blenio	Guardian
Andrea A Marca (AAM)	Centre for dialectology and ethnography / Centro di dialettologia e di etnografia (CDE)	Representative of ethnographic museums
Filippo Jauch (FJ)	Civil protection - Protezione civile 3 valli (PCi 3Valli)	Responsible for cultural heritage

During the meeting the participants had the objective to apply the CHEERS methodology to the Museo Valle di Blenio and to accomplish the task the meeting was organized in four sections:

1. Participants jointly selected 10 of the most representative objects of the museum collection to be evaluated in order to apply the CHEERS Methodology in view of drafting a museum emergency plan (See chapter "Cultural heritage being evaluated").

2. Participants define individually the general weight of values in relation to museum. The coordinator left the participants time to reflect on the percentage of value to be attributed to the entire collection. Then, the values assigned by each participant were collected live, recorded and projected by the coordinator on a wall screen to allow the verification of correctness in the transcription process and related discussion.
3. Participants collectively define the scoring value of the 10 objects previously selected.
4. Participants collectively discussed strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats emerging from the application of the CHEERS evaluation procedures to the Museo Valle di Blenio.

Cristian Scapozza, in his role of CHEERS project referent from SUPSI, collected all the information acquired during the meeting and then he shared an Italian report with results, which has been validated by email by all participants.

Defining the weights

The first step of the evaluation measures the weights of individual types of values, according to the framework provided by the CHEERS project, assessing the:

- *evidential value*: valore probatorio (**VPr**)
- *historic value*: valore storico (**VSt**)
- *aesthetic/artistic value*: valore estetico/artistico (**VEs**)
- *communal value*: valore comunitario/collettivo (**VCo**)
- *economic value*: valore economico (**VEc**)
- *in-use/fruition value*: valore in uso/di fruizione (**VUs**)
- *Scientific/educational value*: valore scientifico/educativo (**VSc**)

The values were translated in Italian for making sure of a common understanding of all participants involved. The definition of “evidential value” was not initially so clear and requested a more precise explanation.

The general discussion within the working group and the personal reflection of each participant in relation the entire collection, made it possible to define the relative weight of each value as follows [in %]:

Tab 5: Results of the weighting of individual types of values based on the assessment of each stakeholder.

Participant	VPr	VSt	VEs	VCo	VEc	VUs	VSc	Sum
Cristian Scapozza	10	20	10	20	5	10	25	100
Patrizia Pusterla Cambin	15	20	20	15	10	5	15	100
Fortunato Pezzatti	5	25	10	25	5	5	25	100
Letizia Genucchi Strazzini	5	15	20	20	5	5	30	100
Andrea A Marca	10	25	5	30	5	5	20	100
Filippo Jauch	5	25	5	30	15	10	10	100
Average	8.33	21.67	11.67	23.33	7.50	6.67	20.83	100

To the collection of the Museo Valle di Blenio is attributed a communal, historical and scientific/educational values with an average of weight that exceed the 20%. As historic-ethnographic museum, its collection is significant for telling the story and the local identity of the area of Blenio Valley, whose importance for the community reaches a weight of over 23%. In addition to the communal and historical values, to the museum is assigned an important scientific and educational value (20.83%), due to his role as archive (important for didactics) and documentation centre where scientific research on the objects and the territory are carried on.

Despite it is impossible to draw quantitative results from the data collected it is possible also to notice that participant with a strong expertise on cultural heritage have attributed a higher weight to the aesthetic and artistic value of the collection (11.67%), respect to participants experiencing the museum from a territorial perspective (a geographer, an ethnographer, and the civil protection representative), more focused on showing the relationship of its objects with the landscape and to his scientific / educational value. Finally, the attribution of an in-use / fruition value, an economic, and evidential value is significantly lower, and it ranges between 6.67 and 8.33%

The average of the weightings proposed by each of the participants is then applied to the evaluation of each single value for the 10 objects selected.

Scoring the values

The definition of the score weights was performed individually, but the asset of cultural heritage was performed by the entire group of stakeholders.

The evaluation of the ten selected objects is presented in the Table 6, where the objects have been classified in descending order of total value.

Tab 6: Table reporting the relative weight of values to each object of the collection.

Code / Asset	VPr	VSt	VEs	VCo	VEc	VUs	VSc	Total
Relative weight of value	0.08	0.22	0.12	0.23	0.08	0.07	0.21	1
LOT-2011.0018 - Ambrosian ostensory	81	243	81	27	81	0	27	86.85
LOT-1992.0444 - Sculpture of apostles	81	81	81	27	81	0	27	51.75
LOT-1998.0014 - Fresco of the Nativity	27	81	27	9	81	0	27	36.75
LOT-1992.0122 - <i>Prea</i> in Baveno granite	27	81	27	9	9	0	27	31.35
LOT-1992.0431 - Brocade tunic	81	27	81	9	27	0	9	28.05
Plaster sculpture "Aurora"	81	3	81	9	81	0	3	25.65
Peasant costume	9	9	27	27	9	0	27	18.45
LOT-1992.0316-0321 - Series of 6 soapstone pans	81	9	3	9	9	0	27	17.45
LOT-2005.0008 - Chocolate maker	27	27	27	9	3	0	9	15.45
LOT-1992.0061 - Mobile step	3	27	3	1	3	0	9	8.78

The outcomes of the scoring value indicate that the *Ambrosian ostensory* (LOT-2011.0018) has the highest priority. The second and third objects to give priority are also related to sacred art: the *Sculpture of apostles*

(LOT-1992.0444) and the *Fresco of the Nativity* (LOT-1998.0014). The historical value attributed in these cases by all participants has been determinant.

The objects that appear in the three subsequent positions, which present a similar score between them, include all three types of objects in the collection: an ethnographic object (*Prea in Baveno granite*), a contemporary art work (*Plaster sculpture "Aurora"*) and sacred art piece (*Brocade tunic*). It should be noted that the size and weight of the objects plays an important role: among the first objects to be evacuated are the heaviest and largest ones which in some cases require two people to be transported (*Sculpture of apostles*, *Fresco of the Nativity*, *Prea in Baveno granite*).

At the bottom of the rank, small ethnographic objects are placed, whose small size and weight would make the evacuation easier and faster in the event of emergency. Finally, it is necessary to mention the importance of the "uniqueness" of the objects as a specific value of the ethnographic collection, which is not included in the evaluation model proposed by the CHEERS methodology. Although the uniqueness of a work can be a rather obvious value for art objects and cultural heritage sites, it is nevertheless a determining criterion in the process of research, selection, conservation and exhibition of ethnographic collection for their unique relation and representation of the territory. This explains the reason why to the objects placed at the last position (*Mobile step* and *Chocolate maker*) is attributed a significant historical value.

Assessing the test outcomes

SWOT Museo della Valle di Blenio		
	Positive	Negative
	<i>Strengths</i>	<i>Weaknesses</i>
Internal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More participatory and transparent involvement in an object selection procedure by all stakeholders. • Obliges to bend down, object by object, on values that consider it in its integrity. • Parameters that, at the average level, give a more quantitative and shareable indication compared to the qualitative selection made by a single expert. • Numerical scale in multiples of three which allows you to differentiate the objects more from each other at the end of the evaluation procedure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of a clear definition of values and their scope. • There is no value that clearly accounts for the uniqueness of the cultural asset (especially in the ethnographic field, a cultural asset may have low overall values, but be unique, as is the example of the object LOT-1992.0061). • In the case of a museum collection, it is necessary to carry out a preliminary skimming that falls outside this procedure.
External	<i>Opportunities</i>	<i>Threats</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It could allow a hierarchy of importance of a series of objects / collection. ● Greater involvement of different skills and sensitivities. ● Ability to involve non-specialists in a targeted manner who can contribute to the creation of a museum installation (permanent or temporary). ● The procedure seems to be more useful in the case of selection of representative objects for a museum layout than for their protection in case of natural danger. ● The procedure allows you to focus attention on this issue, which has often not been addressed in the past, especially for ethnographic objects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● An interaction between the CHEERS procedure and the established procedure for the protection of cultural heritage at civil protection level, which already has a well-established procedure, is required. ● In the case of an ethnographic museum, an interaction / comparison is necessary between the management of a collection by the museum, its direct interaction with the dialectology and ethnography centre, involving the instances responsible for the protection of cultural heritage (a cantonal level, the Office of Cultural Heritage). ● Difficulty in applying a procedure common to the entire Alpine area that can adapt to the administrative / legislative context of each individual state / region.
--	--	---

Identifying (mis-)matches among SWOT element and highlighting strategies for their improvement

- **Strengths/Opportunities (SO):** Thanks to the participatory process and the numerical scale of objects evaluation, the CHEERS tool for assets evaluations is also suitable for use by stakeholders who are not necessarily experts in the evaluation and management of cultural heritage. This can also facilitate its application to the ethnographic context and to object's selection for planning a new museum exhibition.
- **Weaknesses/Opportunities (WO):** The refinement of the procedure, especially concerning a better values definition and the integration of a value considering the uniqueness of the cultural asset, would allow the CHEERS tool for assets evaluations to be equally applied also to ethnographic objects, which at the present time seems to be penalised compared to artistic objects. The purpose of applying the CHEERS tool for assets evaluations in museums should also be specified, as it is unlikely to be suitable for the evaluation of an entire collection (thousands of objects), but it seems more appropriate for the evaluation of a part of the collection (tens/hundred objects), which can be pre-selected either on a typological basis (e.g. for an exhibition) or by experts (e.g. to establish a protection priority).
- **Strengths/Threats (ST):** Participatory involvement is more effective the more stakeholders are involved. It is therefore necessary to integrate all strategic stakeholders in the process, in particular those involved in the protection of cultural heritage (Civil Protection and Cultural Heritage Office – *Ufficio dei beni culturali* UBC), not forgetting the offices responsible for the cantonal museums management (Centre for Dialectology and Ethnography – *Centro di dialettologia e di etnografia* CDE) which, thanks to this case study, were involved for the first time in the application of a tool for cultural assets evaluation.
- **Weaknesses/Threats (WT):** As there are no major mismatches between internal weaknesses and external threats (WT), the application of the CHEERS tool for assets evaluations is not particularly problematic in itself, provided that we consider: (1) the tool refinements derived from the comparison between internal weaknesses and external opportunities (WO), and; (2) the greater involvement of all the strategic stakeholders as postulated by the comparison between internal strengths and external threats (ST).